

FORMATION OF ABILITIES AND SKILLS WITH TRACK AND PEACE ATHLETICS EXERCISES

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Annotation: Athletics have a wide range of effects on the body. They contribute to the solution of health-improving, educational and educational tasks in the process of physical education. They also form the basis for mastering the content of the school curriculum. Physical education lessons help students develop a positive attitude towards physical education activities, as well as attract students to other forms of physical education and sports.

Key words: physical education, lesson, athletics, student.

Introduction. Famous scientists from many countries have devoted their works to the problem of studying the positive attitude of students towards physical education and sports. The authors cover in detail the problems of physical education and the formation of a positive attitude towards physical education and sports [4, 6, 7].

In their research, scientists Ya. M. Abdullaev, Kh. A. Menglikulov, D. Yu. Turdimurodov reveal methods of teaching the technique of motor actions, nurturing the physical qualities of middle school students [1, 2, 3]. European scientists also studied the mechanisms of motor activity control in schoolchildren. However, there is still no clearly formulated theory of controlling the rational motor activity of students in the process of teaching the technique of athletics exercises [5, 8].

Recently, the physical activity of children has been gradually decreasing. Due to the intensification of the learning process, the level of mental load on the neuro-emotional sphere of students increases [9, 12, 14]. At the time of graduation, many

students acquire chronic diseases. In this case, it is not mental work that causes harm, but its companion – the lifestyle is deprived of movements or significantly limited in them [10, 11].

It should be noted that students' interest in systematic classes is decreasing, insufficient educational activities of physical education teachers in class and outside of class hours, imperfect methods of conducting physical education lessons and monotony, low level of emotionality in classes, insufficient promotion of a healthy lifestyle and the formation of interest in physical education exercises [13, 15].

In the educational field "Health and Physical Education" the following tasks are expected to be solved:

- developing in students knowledge about health, a healthy lifestyle, safe behavior, physical education, physical exercise, the relationship of the human body with the natural and social environment;
- formation and development of skills of basic general developmental motor actions;
- development of active motivation in students to take care of their own health and engage in physical education, improve the physical, social, mental and spiritual components of health;
- instilling in students the need for health, which is an important value, and a conscious desire to lead a healthy lifestyle;
- development of skills to independently make decisions about one's own actions;
- students' acquisition of their own health-saving experience, taking into account their health status;
- use in everyday life the experience of health-saving activities for one's own health and the health of other people.

One of the most important areas of implementation of state policy in the field of physical education is physical education in secondary schools. It is noted that physical education in our state is an integral part of the national education system, an important component of humanitarian education, the formation of patriotic feelings, physical and moral health, and the improvement of the physical and

psychological preparation of schoolchildren for active life and professional activities [16, 18].

It is during this period that the necessary skills and abilities to use appropriate means in everyday life are formed, the motives and needs of an active motor mode are realized. The educational process in physical education is based on the principles of science, humanism, democracy, continuity and continuity, independence from the interference of any political parties, other public and religious organizations [17,19, 20].

An important task of physical education of children and adolescents is the development of physical qualities that contribute to the comprehensive harmonious development of the individual and increase the adaptive capabilities of the body. The main means of physical education are physical exercises, with the help of which schoolchildren develop vital skills and abilities, develop physical qualities, develop physical abilities, increase the adaptive qualities of the body, and restore previously lost functions.

The main form of organizing children's physical education at school is the lesson. It is in physical education lessons that schoolchildren acquire knowledge, skills, the ability to perform morning hygienic gymnastics, physical education minutes, games and exercises during breaks, condition the body, and independently engage in physical exercises at their place of residence in order to increase the level of their physical fitness.

Physical education lessons should contribute to the formation of a positive attitude towards physical education in schoolchildren, as well as to attract schoolchildren to other forms of physical education and sports.

Recently, more and more negative information has been received about the increase in the number of accidents among schoolchildren during physical education lessons. These circumstances forced the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan to make a decision to temporarily reduce the workload of schoolchildren

in the process of physical exercise and refuse to accept control standards. First of all, this concerns the acceptance of standards for running, both for speed and endurance. According to medical observations, every second schoolchild has various deviations in his health. Annual examinations of school students indicate an increasing trend in the number of diseases and disorders in the functioning of all body systems, including such vital ones as the cardiovascular and respiratory systems.

The age-related development of the musculoskeletal system, metabolism and energy, the activity of internal organs, the psyche and emotional-volitional qualities largely depends on the volume, intensity and qualitative characteristics of the child's motor regime. Under the influence of muscle activity in childhood, the foundation of health and longevity is laid.

Athletics is the most popular sport that promotes the comprehensive physical development of a person, since it combines common and vital movements (walking, running, jumping, throwing). As a full-fledged sport, it is distinguished by its versatility and the ability to develop not just one part of the body, but all together. The very practice of athletics exercises has great health-improving, educational, educational and applied significance. Health-improving tasks include: promoting the harmonious development of the body (formation of correct posture, development of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, activation of metabolic processes, strengthening of the nervous system), development of motor qualities, hardening of the body. While running and walking, a large number of skeletal muscles are brought into play, conditions are created for the formation of correct posture and the development of internal organs, especially the cardiovascular and respiratory systems. The health value of athletics is also enhanced by the fact that they are held outdoors.

Thus, athletics facilities contribute to the solution of health-improving, educational and educational tasks in the process of physical education. They form the basis for mastering the content of the school curriculum and have significant

advantages in organization and widespread use, since they do not require special conditions or equipment.

In the practice of school physical education, the main indicator of the effectiveness of mastering motor skills and abilities should be the degree of mastery of movements, the completeness of awareness of the largest number of their components. Knowledge of these provisions allows us to assume that in all cases only the task of the action is deeply understood, and the action itself in its mechanical manifestation is performed automatically. Since the specific task of an action determines the essence of its technique, we can assume that in the process of forming motor skills and abilities, all elements of the technique of athletics exercises turn into a fact of consciousness. As for the internal essence of movement, its internal mechanisms, they function automatically.

Conclusions. An analysis of the scientific literature on this issue revealed that athletics occupy a leading position among others in the development of physical qualities of students. They have a wide range of effects on the body, contribute to the solution of health-improving, educational and educational tasks in the process of physical education. Conducting physical education lessons with the predominant use of athletics contributes to the initial training of children in a comprehensive school, as well as the formation of a sports lifestyle for younger schoolchildren.

References:

1. Abdullaev, Y. M., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Creation of pedagogical conditions in the formation of volitional grades in primary school students. *Colloquium-journal*.
2. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(3)*, 2021.

3. Mahkamjonovich, A. Y. (2021). Forms and methods of developing the use of folk movement games in high school students. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 73-79.
4. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
5. Mahkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Technology of using outdoor games in the development of physical qualities of junior schoolchildren.
6. Mahkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Innovative Approaches to the Formation of the Voluntary Qualities of Students-Athletes. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 17-20.
7. Mahkamovich AY. Mobile games for school children. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 2022;4:202-5.
8. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF SPORTS SELECTION IN BOXING. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 192-168.
9. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
10. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24-2, pp. 14-16). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.
11. Абдуллаев, Я. М. (2012). Развитие физического воспитания подрастающего поколения в непрерывном образовании. *Молодой ученый*, (11), 381-383.

12. Абдуллаев, Я. М. (2021, October). Особенности развития физических качеств у учеников старшего школьного возраста средствами подвижных игр. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 523-525).

13. Абдуллаев, Я. (2023). Юқори синф ўқувчиларида ноанъанавий ҳаракатли ўйинлар орқали ҳаракат сифатларини ривожлантириш. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/S), 61-67.

14. Абдуллоев, Я. М. (2022). Бошланғич синф ўқувчиларда инсоний фазилатларни ноанъанавий миллий ҳаракатли ўйинлардан воситасининг шакллантириш педагогик шарт-шароитлари: Абдуллоев Яшнаржон Махкамович, Термиз давлат университети Спорт бошқаруви кафедраси ўқитувчиси. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (12/2), 180-183.

15. Менглиқулов, Х. А. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, Учредители: Общественная организация. Институт социальной трансформации*, 104-107.

16. Менглиқулов, Х. А. (2021). Мактабда жисмоний тарбиянинг дарсдан ташқари фаолиятини ташкиллаштириш ва унинг шакллари. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, 3(9), 77.

17. Менглиқулов, Х. (2023). Harakatli o'yinlar orqali 14-15 yoshli suzuvchilarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirish. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 230-236.

18. Менглиқулов, Х. А. (2022). Ёш сузувчиларни ўргатишнинг бошланғич босқичида танловнинг назарий жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (8 (117)), 55-59.

19. Менглиқулов, Х. (2022). 14-15 ёшдаги сузувчиларда тезлик-куч сифатларини ривожлантириш услубиёти. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 81-87.

20. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире Учредители: Общественная организация" Институт социальной трансформации*, 140-144.